

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF WRESTLING

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ABSTRACT

The article tells about the struggle for our national values, its history, the role and significance of sport, especially wrestling, in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation. At the same time, information was analyzed about many famous wrestlers who grew up in our country, about the reforms carried out in our country in the field of sports.

Key words: wrestling, values, history of sports, Ministry of Tourism and Sports, "Umid Nihollari", "Barkamol Avlod", "Universiada", youth development.

INTRODUCTION

In training sessions with young wrestlers, Gorogli's physical strength, his physical abilities, his qualities, his ability to endure in difficult conditions, and the help of his physical training are examples of our national values. In addition, we consider it appropriate to provide information about the physical strength, physical and moral qualities of Muhammad Pahlavan and Mahmud the wrestler, who lived and worked in the territory of our Republic and showed the best examples of wrestling.

The fight, which has attracted the attention of millions, has its deep historical roots as one of the highest spiritual values of the world.

MAIN PART

The Uzbek people have a great respect for wrestlers, because they embody bravery, courage, endurance, moral purity, and courage.

The name of Pahlavon Mahmud from Khorezm (1243-1326) has an eternal place in history. One of the great leaders of Futuvvat-juvanmardlik group. He wrote in Persian. He was engaged in post-indigo and telpak-doz [1]. Throughout his life, he never lost in competitions. Wrestler Mahmud traveled to many countries, visited Iran, India and many other Eastern countries, traveled throughout Central Asia and fought with strong wrestlers everywhere. But nowhere, neither in his homeland nor in foreign lands, did his shovel touch the ground.

Pahlavon Mahmud was not only a wrestler-wrestler, but also a poet, thinker, mature person in all respects. He embodied high moral qualities, humanity and physical perfection.

After Pahlavon Mahmud's death, a little more than a hundred years later, another wrestler - Pahlavon Muhammad - lived in Khorezm. Like his predecessor, he did not know what defeat was.

Ahmed Polvan from Tashkent was also very famous among the people. In 1895, the famous German wrestler Rippel came to Tashkent and expressed his desire to fight with Ahmed. On June 23, 1895, a fight will take place in the circus arena and it will end with a great victory of the Uzbek wrestler. They compete in classical wrestling. It is noteworthy that Ahmed the

wrestler did not attend any school of wrestling except national wrestling. But despite this, he won precisely in classical wrestling thanks to his strength, endurance and high fighting skills.

In 1911, Ahmed the wrestler took part in the French wrestling competition for the first time and won against the German champion Huegner.

Toji Aloyev, born in Tashkent in 1890, successfully participated in the circus arena. Taji Ahmad was a student of the wrestler. It is interesting that in 1919, the Tazhi wrestler, who had no special training in classical wrestling, won in his weight class in the competition held in this type of wrestling. Since 1942, Toji Aloyev began to perform his art in the Uzbek circus. There are many famous wrestlers in the republic. Hero of Labor Hakim wrestler Kadyrov successfully fought in the heavyweight division for a quarter of a century.

Ismail Turobov, born in 1937 in Bukhara region, master of sports in freestyle and classical wrestling, as well as Uzbek wrestling, is a generational representative of national wrestling.

Fighting has become a family tradition for the Turobovs. His father, grandfather and uncle were famous wrestlers before. His father, Turob Sharobov, and his uncle, Bahrom Sharobov, were wrestlers who successfully participated in national wrestling competitions. All of them were excellent blacksmiths. Bukhara emir Amir Olimkhan invited them to serve as wrestlers in his palace. But the wrestlers refused to serve the emir and suffered him many times [3].

The family tradition, the relay of generations, will be passed on to the sons of wrestlers Turob and Bahram. Ismail Turobov received good training in his family at a young age, good physical development, good knowledge of national wrestling techniques paved the way for Ismail to enter the big sports field - he perfectly mastered the Olympic types of wrestling and won three national, freestyle and classical wrestling championships. once received the title of master of sports. In 1957, Ismail Turobov successfully participated in the championship of the former union in freestyle wrestling held in Tbilisi. That year was the year for Ismail to reach the pinnacle of his sports skills: he participated in sports festivals in Tashkent and Moscow. From 1958 to 1969, Ismail was the champion of Uzbekistan in freestyle wrestling, and from 1956 to 1960, the champion of national wrestling.

Ismail Turobov defended the sports honor of our country on international arenas and traveled the glorious path of sports victories. In 1961, Ismail, who won over the wrestlers of Czechoslovakia, Poland, Bulgaria and other countries, became the winner of the international match and took part in the friendly match held in Kabul, the capital of Afghanistan, in the same year. From 1959 to 1964, Ismail Turobov was the captain of the national wrestling team of Uzbekistan.

Kashkadarya region has prepared many great wrestlers-athletes for Uzbek sports. One of them is Sayfiddin Hodiyyev. The great sports path he traveled was complicated and difficult. One day there was a wrestling competition. As a rule, not only adults but also children take part in it. Raim, the son of the Khadiyevs' neighbor, quickly knocked down all the children.

He graduated from high school and entered the Tashkent Institute of Physical Education. In his student years, Sayfiddin wants to practice in the sambo club. But for sambo, his weight is not enough (in those years, sambo did not have a weight up to 48 kg).

That's why he joins the free wrestling circle. Ye here. B. Koltunov coached. Good physical fitness, perfect knowledge of wrestling techniques allowed Saifiddin Khodiyev to become national champion twice: among youth in the first year, and among adults in the second year.[4]

On July 26, 1974, the World Championship was opened in Ulaanbaatar. S. Hodiyevev wins over famous sambo players from Bulgaria, Ukraine, Iran, Turkey, South Korea, and England. But in the final Saifiddin was awaited by a serious opponent - Mongolian champion, two-time international tournament winner Shokdar Monokhul. The meeting was intense and difficult. Even so, the Uzbek athlete defeated his opponent with a score of 10:2. He became the world champion in sambo and brought the first gold medal to the team.

Wrestler Sabir Kurbanov also gained great fame. Since 1973, international tournaments and championships occupy an important place in the sports biography of Sabir Kurbanov. At the European Championship in Madrid, he won a great victory over the Frenchman George Pocat, the Englishman Kilray, the Bulgarian Danov, the Dutchman Dolman, and the Spanish Jose Chechin.

Sabir Kurbanov was awarded the diploma of the European Championship in 1974 and the "Gate of Spain" prize for his high skills and extraordinary sports technique.

In 1974, in an international friendly match held in Ulaanbaatar, Sabir Kurbanov won over the famous world champion, Mongolian wrestler G. Batsukh. Neither the audience nor Batsukh himself considered Sabir a serious opponent. A medium-sized, slow, restrained, polite young man gave the impression of a shy student. Of course, no one doubted that Batsukh would win. But Sabir Kurbanov attacked very quickly and stunned his opponent. Batsukh was unable to repel successive attacks. Speed, agility, strength, will to victory, organization were the characteristics of Sabir Kurbanov in this fight. In a special way, he picked up Batsukh from the ground and lifted him up and threw him to the ground. This method was a completely new method in wrestling, and it was named "Kurbanov twist". At the World Championship held in Minsk in September 1975, Sabir Kurbanov defeated five sambo fighters, including the world champion Batsukh, and received the title of world sambo champion.

Sabir Kurbanov is not only a talented wrestler, but also an experienced coach. He has trained many masters of sports so far.

There is a dynasty of wrestlers in Uzbekistan, whose art of wrestling is passed down from generation to generation. Yusupov family lives in Karakul district of Bukhara region. People call this family "Bahodir family". It's not for nothing, of course. There are six former masters of sports of the USSR in the family. Their grandfather Rozmat was a legendary wrestler, the people called him Invincible. His grandson Tursun Yusupov was a strong and dexterous hero. He taught all his seven sons the art of wrestling. Even in his old age, he was a well-known wrestler in the region. He trained his sons and taught them how to fight.

Values represent various social, economic and spiritual aspects of human life. Values are material and spiritual, national and universal.

Among them, the Uzbek nation has its own values. In particular, Uzbek wrestling is a masterpiece of our national value. Currently, a number of practical works have been carried out to introduce Uzbek wrestling to the world. First of all, the presidential decree of February 1999 "On support of the International Wrestling Association" is an example.

Currently, an international wrestling association has been established and more than 100 countries have joined it. More than 120 countries have recognized the International Wrestling Association and are working together. Uzbek words related to wrestling: dakki, chala, halal, reprimand, yanbosh, kurush, tokhta, time, etc. are resounding on the sports fields of the world.

In recent years, the Uzbek National Wrestling Federation, the International Wrestling Association, and the Ministry of Tourism and Sports have been implementing a number of activities for the development of Uzbek wrestling.

During the years of independence, international memorial tournaments traditionally held in the cities of Shakhrisabz, Bukhara, Termiz, and Khiva served to develop wrestling. Also, the following measures were taken to further develop the struggle:

From December 10, 1999 to January 10, 2000, the month of wrestling was held under the slogan "Struggle is my pride".

A series of competitions held under the slogans "Wrestlers on the carpet", "Wrestlers never age", "Wrestling does not choose age" did not leave fans of wrestling indifferent.

In order to further promote wrestling, contests on "Uzbek wrestling to the Olympics" and "I will use Uzbek wrestling" were announced. This contest was constantly advertised on television and radio. At the end of the competition, he once again shows his love for the struggle of the Uzbek people.

Uzbek wrestling takes place in three-level sports competitions held in our republic, i.e.: between universities "Universiade" between academic lyceums and vocational colleges between students of "Barkamol Avlod" school taking a place in the "Umid Nihollar" event shows that our struggle has become popular. Currently, there are 329 secondary schools in the public education system of Uzbekistan. Today's sports in these schools require students to reflect our national values, to be hardworking, to be self-controlled, to overcome negative emotions, and to overcome difficulties on the way to the goal set before them. Sports competitions are also very important. The rules of the competition force the athletes to fight with the opponent in strictly defined conditions. A young wrestler is required not only to be disciplined, honest and truthful, but also to respect his opponent and sports referees.

CONCLUSION

Today, Uzbek wrestling spread its glory to the world. He introduced the Uzbek people to the world. A number of terms used in this national game are heard in almost every corner of the world.

At the root of all this, we can say that the restoration of our national values, which have been inherited from our ancestors until today, has accelerated considerably.

At the same time, the Uzbek nation, the Uzbek language and other national traditions are known and recognized by many countries in the world.

Relying on the best experiences of the international sports movement, physical culture in Uzbekistan is being watered with spiritual-educational culture based on values, and in turn, they are serving our values and spiritual-educational processes.

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